

Animal detection using SSD model with Raspberry pi for vehicles

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Abstract. Animal detection is an emerging field of interest now a days. Movement of animals are detected for many purposes. Sometimes animals are detected for saving their lives near highway and railway trucks. Sometimes they are traced on fields and need to drive them away in order to save the crops. This paper is an approach towards detection the animals using mobile net from moving vehicles. Raspberry pi which is suitable for the SSD model has been used here. An alarm has been generated here on the detection of an animal. COCO dataset has been used here for the detection.

Keywords. Object Detection, SSD model, Common Objects in Context (COCO) dataset, Opencv, Raspberrypi, Sensors.

1. Introduction:

Human can easily detect and identify an object from an image or a real time video. But it is very difficult for a machine to identify or detect an object. The process of identifying an object from an image or real time video is called object detection. There are many object detection algorithms available at present. The algorithms popularly used in object detection are YOLO, SSD,

RCNN etc. SSD model with COCO can identify 80 objects, but among these objects only the animals are detected in this research work. The main aim of this project is to protect causalities of animals on roads. Animal accident is a severe problem these days. A Raspberry pi with a camera is mounted on a vehicle which captures real time video. When an animal is detected then an alarm is generated for the driver such that the driver get alert for nearby animals and take necessary actions for avoiding accidents.

2. Related work:

Wie Liu et al worked on a model which detects objects in images using a single deep neural network. They used SSD which discretized the output space of bounding boxes into a set of default boxes over different aspect ratios and scales per feature map location [1].

Elham Mohammed Thabit at al proposed a model for automated mammals detection using SSD mobile net. In this work they have collected 2000 from the standard dataset (such as Caltech 101) and the net. The SSD framework improves the detection and recognition processes of Convolution Neural Network (CNN) [2]

Ashwani Kumar et al develop a model which is composed of multiple layers to classify a given object they have used convolutional neural network (CNN) to developed this model. To speed up the computational performance of object detection they have used single shot multi box detector algorithm along with the help of architecture of faster region convolutional neural network [3].

Joseph Redmon et al worked on a new approach on object detection named YOLO. Here a single neural network predicts bounding boxes and class probabilities directly from full image in one evaluation. The whole detection pipeline is a single network; hence it can be optimized end to end directly on detection performance [4].

Chengcheng Ning et al propose a method Inception SSD(I-SSD) in which they improve the efficiency of the SSD algorithm. Here they adopt an Inception block to replace all the extra layers in SDD.[5]

Aswini Kumar et al proposed a model to increase the classification accuracy of the SSD model. In the proposed model they have used multilayers to classify the given objects.[6]

3. Objective:

Figure 1: High performance computing device.

In particular, the approach in this paper is development of a device that collects images or videos of animals if they move in an unsafe or sensitive area. Then the image or video data will be sent as input to a high-performance computing power device, then after processing that image or video, an expected output such as an animal entering the sensitive area, if any such output comes, then the signal will appear on a display on the device in this way we can set an alarm.

Here a microcontroller is need which will collect output signal from computer and convert into human readable signal such as display, alarm etc.

4. Existing system and problems:

There are some this type of device is already exists but there are some problems in there such as total systems (input, output and processing) work in same location, a diagram is given here:

Figure 2: Conceptual diagram of animal detection device

Figure 3: Animal detection device (Existing)^[8]

5. Modified Design:

Figure 4: Modified design of animal detection device.

This modified design shows that, we have three different parts of whole system.

1.Sensitive area: The main area of environments, where we connect all type of sensor as like as camera for collecting video data and it send to Computational area for processing.

2.Computational area: collect data from one or more sensitive area and process it (multiple process can happen simultaneously) for proper output which need to cast to one or multiple Output area.

3.Output area: this area collects proper output from high config Computational area and convert proper output signal through a microcontroller.

Figure 5: Demo device (image captured from Ip camera) developed.

5.1 Device description and our Lab works:

The all-Lab works Happen two parts:

1. Image Processing.
2. Collecting I/O and implement in Hardware Device.

Some electronic device is important for making this project such as: Ip camera, Microcontroller, Lcd (for showing output) and a high config computer device.

5.2 Flow diagram of this animal detection device:

Figure 6: Block diagram of modified device.

6.Methodology.

The camera is mounted on the vehicle and it captures real time video of the surroundings. When an animal is detected by the model (SSD) then the model returns a specific numerical value

for every detected animal to the raspberry pi. A Red LED (Light Emitting Diode) and 16X2 display is connected with raspberry pi. An alarm for the driver of the vehicle is generated if an animal is identified. Based on the values getting from model (SSD) LCD displays the name of the animal appeared closed to the vehicle. Workflow of the complete process is shown below-

Figure 7: Working flow diagram.

The devices like Web camera, LED and 16x2 display are connected to the raspberry pi. Raspberry is a single board CPU which is popularly used in different types of projects.

6.1 The Single Shot Detector (SSD) model.

The SSD approach is based on a feed-forward convolutional network which produces a collection of bounding boxes and scores for the objects present in the bounding boxes; it is followed by a non-maximum suppression step to produce the final detection.

Figure 8: Architecture of SSD Model [5]

In the above model the input image is feed to VGG-16 network which extracts the features of the image. After that a series of convolution layer will create multiple bounding boxes for each object detected. And finally Non-Maximum Suppression remove the duplicate bounding boxes and detect the object by using maximum confidence value.

6.2 The Raspberry Pi.

Raspberry pi is an efficient and powerful mini computer developed by Raspberry Pi Foundation, United Kingdom. It is popularly used in projects like Image processing, Internet of Things (IOT), Robotics, Object Detection and many more. From the invention (2012) of Raspberry multiple models has been launched such that Model B (2012), Model B+(2014), Model 3B (2018), Model 4B (2021). Among the models we have used Model 4B with 2GB Ram for our project.

6.2.1 Specification of Raspberry Pi Model 4B(Used Model).

Processor: Quad-core Cortex-A72,64-bit,1.5GHz

Ram: 1GB,2GB,4GB,8GB

Connectivity: Bluetooth 5.0

2.4Ghz and 5.0GHz IEEE 802.11ac wireless LAN

BLE Gigabit Ethernet

GPIO pin: Total 40 GPIO pins.

7.Result.

Here in this projects COCO (Common Objects in Context) [7] has been used. SSD model with COCO dataset can identify 80 classes of objects. Among these 80 objects only the animals and person are filtered. Each class of objects has a specific class 'id'. When an object is detected then the model returns the specific class 'id'. And using this class id all the sensors are connected to get an alarm for the driver of the vehicle. Here the model can detect the following animals in real time-

Class Id	Object Name
0	[Nothing]
1	Person
17	Cat
18	Dog
19	Horse
20	Sheep
21	Cow
22	Elephant
23	Beer
24	Zebra
25	Giraffe

Table1: Class Id of each object detected.

Following are the results of animal detection by using web camera or by android mobile camera.

Figure-9: Cow detected from camera.

Figure-10: A dog detected

Figure-11: Person detected

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8.Conclusion.

In this paper the SSD object detection model for object detection using Raspberry pi has been proposed and used. SSD is a lightweight algorithm which can run on raspberry pi easily. This model can be used in various fields to solve some real-life problems like object detection and object classification. Here in this paper this model has been created to identify only animals enlisted above table 1.SSD model with COCO dataset can identify total 80 objects but here only the listed objects among 80 objects are extracted out.